

THE INTERTEXTUALITY OF SYMBOLS IN LITERATURE

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Abstract. *Transtextuality and intertextuality are two critical concepts in literary theory that deal with the complex relationships between texts. While they share common ground, each focuses on distinct aspects of these connections. The analysis of intertextuality underscores the idea that texts are not isolated entities but exist in a web of connections, where meaning is generated through these relationships. Symbolic elements are often key to exploring intertextuality, as they act as bridges between texts. Through the recognition of these symbols—whether they are motifs, archetypes, or recurring themes—readers can trace the connections that form a network of meaning across different works.*

Keys: *transtextuality, intertextuality, symbols.*

Annatsiya. *Intertekstuallik (Matnlararo bog'liqlik) va transtekstuallik adabiyot nazariyasidagi ikkita muhim tushuncha bo'lib, ular matnlar orasidagi murakkab munosabatlarni o'rganadi. Ular umumiy jihatlarni bo'lishsa-da, har biri bu aloqalarning turli jihatlari e'tibor qaratadi. Matnlararo tahlil matnlar yakkalanmagan ob'ektlar emas, balki ular o'rtasida bog'lanishlar mavjud bo'lgan tarmoqda mavjud ekanligi g'oyasini ta'kidlaydi. Bu bog'lanishlar ma'no yaratadi. Ramziy elementlar matnlararo aloqalarni o'rganishda asosiy ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, ular matnlar orasidagi ko'prik sifatida xizmat qiladi. Ushbu ramzlarni—ular motivlar, arxetiplar yoki takrorlanuvchi mavzular bo'lishidan qat'i nazar—tan olish orqali o'quvchilar turli asarlar o'rtasida ma'no tarmog'ini kuzatishlari mumkin. Shu tarzda, ham transtekstuallik, ham intertekstuallik orasidagi o'zaro ta'sirni ta'kidlaydi. Bu hodisa bizning adabiyotga dinamik, bir-biriga bog'langan hikoyalar, g'oyalar va ramzlar tizimi sifatida tushunishimizni oshiradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *transtekstuallik, intertekstuallik, ramziy belgilar.*

Аннотация. *Транстекстуальность и интертекстуальность — два важнейших понятия в теории литературы, которые касаются сложных отношений между текстами. Хотя они имеют общие точки зрения, каждый из них фокусируется на различных аспектах этих связей. Анализ интертекстуальности подчеркивает идею о том, что тексты не являются изолированными сущностями, а существуют в сети связей, где смысл генерируется посредством этих отношений. Символические элементы часто являются ключом к исследованию интертекстуальности, поскольку они служат мостами между текстами. Благодаря распознаванию этих символов — будь то мотивы, архетипы или повторяющиеся темы — читатели могут проследить связи, которые образуют сеть значений в различных произведениях.*

Ключевые слова: *транстекстуальность, интертекстуальность, символические знаки.*

Introduction

For many decades, literature has been recognized as a domain of types and, more importantly, of symbols, which are the basic thoughts and ideas of specific themes and serve a purpose as a tool for conveying complex moods and relationships. It is through intertextuality, then, these symbols in various literary works begin to be the center of study. Although the term may not be well-established, intertextuality suggests the idea that all texts are language and that none lives in isolation of the other, in fact every text gets nourished as well as nourishes itself out

of a broader matrix of texts. Textual intertextuality of symbols in literature, for instance, helps to understand how these authors use the symbols that had been created previously to construct new meanings in their own writings. This pursuit leads to the expansion of the translation range and therefore the enriching of the author's style allows one to better understand the text structures and the intricacies of woven meaning in the literary world.

Definitions of Transtextuality and Intertextuality in Literature

Grard Genette's wide concept of transtextuality includes many other inter-textual dimensions including: paratextuality, metatextuality, hypertextuality, and archi-textuality, beyond the intertextuality that he has discussed. Understanding more clearly the network of relations in which texts are implicated and to which they are related is made possible by this extreme concept of the textual discourse. For instance, hypertextuality deals with the transformation of older texts through pastiche and adaptation while newly created ones remain dominant, while paratextuality comes to deal with the relations between the body of a text and its texts in the form of key headings, forewords, poscripts, and engravings. It underlines that every books come from some body of literature or some culture and culture and none comes from nowhere. This connection deepens the significance of certain authorship by other works to the same making their conversation possible. It can take many forms including direct quotes, references, evocative parallels, or mere stylistic resemblance. Julia Kristeva was the first to use the term intertextuality, which plays emphasis on the aspect of texts informing and using each other.[5]

Understanding the more encompassing notion of transtextuality makes it possible to conduct a more complex inquiry into the relations that exist among texts in their multiple aspects – intertextual relations. This is important to literature and its interpretations because it makes visible the ways in which writers quote, respond to or challenge previous texts.

Intertextuality is the literary relationship two or more texts share in that the response of a text produces another text or a web of texts. So that it also uses other writings allusions references borrowings for giving the reading a better experience and for making the original work more profound. Inter:text can range from quotations to self-reflexive references to cultural texts or tropes, or a recalled, weak signaled writing earlier. Other books can be opened in order to make the readers discuss different works of literature as the author can combine the components of the literature works into a single work to make people notice the idea behind it. This intertextual den brings more fascination for the readers to relate with other texts and traditions and in the end will produce the best understanding of the literary work being focused on. [2]

Intertextuality emphasizes how texts can affect and shape one another and emphasizes how interrelated literature is. However, while transtextuality is essential for identifying textual connections, the term "intertextuality" does not encompass a broad variety of concepts. The French structuralist Grard Genette (1930–2018) came up with the more general word "transtextuality," which refers to all types of textual transcendence or connections between texts. It is a more comprehensive paradigm for literary study since it encompasses not only intertextuality but also other kinds of text interactions. Five categories of transtextuality are distinguished by Gerald Genette:

1. **Intertextuality:** The first category ,as described above, direct or indirect textual references.

2. **Paratextuality:** The relationship between the main text and its paratexts (titles, prefaces, epilogues, footnotes, etc.) that help frame or interpret the main text.
3. **Metatextuality:** A critical commentary of one text on another, often without directly quoting the other text (e.g., a critical review or literary critique).
4. **Architextuality:** The generic or thematic relationship that places a text within a specific genre or category (e.g., "romance," "tragedy," "epic").
5. **Hypertextuality:** The relationship between a "hypertext" (new text) and a "hypotext" (an earlier text) that it derives from, transforms, or adapts. Examples include parodies, sequels, and adaptations.

From the above discussion intertextuality can be identified as one of the attributes of transtextuality and intertextuality tends to restrict the kinds of textual relation. Defining the term of transtextuality, it is possible to provide an example of *Wide Sargasso Sea* by Jean Rhys as hypertext linked to *Jane Eyre* by Charlotte Brontë because re-creates the story of Bertha Mason, the secondary character in the precedent novel. *Wide Sargasso Sea* as a hypertext of Charlotte Brontë's *Jane Eyre*, as it reimagines the story of Bertha Mason, a minor character in the original novel.

Intertextuality is the relation between two or more texts whether the texts is literary or non-literary. It was first used in the 1960s by Julia Kristeva who based the term on concepts first developed by Mikhail Bakhtin. Intertextuality means that any text – whether knowingly or not – is a collage of other texts.[2]

Intertextuality refers to the way texts (literary or otherwise) reference, influence, or are interconnected with other texts. The term was popularized by Julia Kristeva in the 1960s, drawing from ideas of Mikhail Bakhtin. Intertextuality suggests that any text is a mosaic of references to or quotations from other texts, whether consciously or unconsciously.

There are several forms of intertextuality in literature:

1. **Direct Quotation:** When a text explicitly quotes another text.
2. **Allusion:** An indirect reference to another text, usually without explicit acknowledgment.
3. **Parody:** A text that humorously imitates another text.
4. **Pastiche:** A text that imitates the style of another text or multiple texts, usually as a celebration rather than for humor or critique.
5. **Adaptation:** A text that reinterprets or reimagines another text in a different form or context.

In *James Joyce's Ulysses*, there is a complex network of intertextual references to *Homer's Odyssey*, among other works. Another , Dan Brawn's “*Da Vince Code*” the Holy Grail can be connected to best-selling author Sylvia Browne, *The Two Marys: The Hidden History of the Mother and Wife of Jesus*.[4]

Intertextuality of Symbols in Literature

Inter textual reference in literature deals with intertextual relation where there exist concept of two or more work so that reference has been made to other works within literature. In this context, symbols help to build these connections and enhance the story within this framework. In the way, the use of the symbols from various texts, the authors can expand the meaning and the impact of the work. For instance, while one text, the symbol for a rose entails the feeling of love and beauty, the other, it is a symbol for secrecy or death. Thus, intertext as writers can put into their works a system of signs that are appealing to readers at various levels of signification. According to As, intertextuality creates the possibility of the texts dialogue:

intensifies the reading; expands the spectrum of interpretations. Thus there is a purpose of the reciprocally related symbols and meaning within the context of literature: to enrich a work and to help the reader better understand and appreciate a text.

Symbols participate one of the most important roles for the representation of various significant conceptions and feelings in the literature. While these display the linguistic aspects of reading, the symbols figured into these tend to be universal sometimes encouraging the reader to relate personally with what is being read. For instance, the use of the color white in Herman Melville's "Moby Dick" is used in double sense as purity and death or even in Steinbeck's, "Sweet Thursday" the author uses the character of Mary's as a symbol of appearance as being innocent but deep down a harlot. The authors subjugate symbols that serve as the guidelines that can be used to read the intended text from by the reader into the realm of their imagination. Besides, symbolism is semiotic so readers can interpret signs in various ways which expands overall grasp of the text at hand. As it has been postulated, symbols extend from the measured rationale of the conscious world and include the preconsciousness by referring to archetypal concepts which may be laid down in readers' subconsciousness. Thus, the value of symbols cannot be overestimated, as they help to add the layer of meaning and improve literature.[1]

Implications of Intertextuality in Symbolism

Symbolic intertextuality calls forth a wealth of potentialities which enhance the value and semantic potential of the text. Thus, referring to texts and cultural signs, authors saturate their symbols with meanings that can be revealed at one or another level to readers. This interconnection between texts enabled a richer analytical commentary of themes and ideas within and across separate texts and the creation of self-referential structures that enrich the interpretation of symbols. In addition, intertextuality poses a critique over the authorial originality since the texts are written in sequence and not within the framework of an archaic creation. By these entwining symbols, writers are able to talk to the tradition of literature, reimposing the classic themes and motifs in another way. This semantic implication of intertextuality witnesses to the unity of the literary context and does not hide recalling people to its eternal actuality. In conclusion, intertextual aspects of symbolization reveal the context-dependent and indeed contextual nature of much literary analysis.

There are common symbols in literature that over ages passes through generation they are:

...*red rose* – a symbol of love and loyalty, *green leaf* – growth, life
pentacle – a five point star, the equality of gender, feminism,
a white dove - can represent peace, *ravens* – may symbolize death or bad omens,
four aspects of life – *water, fire, ground, air*, *the moon* -can symbolize femininity, mystery and etc.[3]

Conclusion

Therefore, the use of intertextual signs in literature is a useful technique of adding great value to a text. In other words, in order to construct multiple layers of meaning, authors are able to refer to shared cultural memories. This paper explores how, by attaining the control of symbols writers are employed to portray such a vast of feelings and aspects; enhancing the reading interests. Secondly, intertextual symbols promote the possibility of integrating various literary works and establish numerous channels of semiosis as a single piece of intertextual sign. This paper has therefore shown that symbols like the garden, the serpent and the journey in different texts are universal due to the following reasons. At last, intertextuality of symbols

contributes to multiple benefits and values which represent literariness of the work, multiple meanings, and interpretation of the text for a reader. (Maurice Beebe, 1960)

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